

DECEPTWIN: Proactive Security Approach for IoV by Leveraging Deception-based Digital Twins and Blockchain

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ABSTRACT

The proliferation of security threats in connected systems necessitates innovative approaches to enhance security resilience. The Internet of Vehicles (IoV) presents a rapidly evolving and interconnected ecosystem that raises unprecedented security challenges, including remote hijacking, data breaches, and unauthorized access. Digital Twin (DT) and blockchain-based deception can emerge as a promising approach to enhance the security of the IoV ecosystem by creating a secure, realistic, dynamic, and interactive deceptive environment that can deceive and disrupt malicious actors. In accordance with this, we propose a proactive security approach for IoV by leveraging **DECEPT**-based **digital** **TW**ins and **blockchaIN** (DECEPTWIN) that entails hunting for security threats and gaps in IoV security posture before an incident or breach occurs.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Security and privacy** → *Intrusion detection systems.*

KEYWORDS

Digital Twin (DT), Blockchain, Deception, Information Security, Internet of Vehicles (IoV), Threat Intelligence (TI)

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Vehicles (IoV) has been gaining traction to transform Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), bringing unprecedented connectivity and efficiency [6, 15]. IoV leverages the Internet of Things (IoT), sensors, roadside infrastructure, and advanced computing to enable real-time data sharing, traffic management, autonomous driving capabilities, and enhancing transportation services for intelligent mobility solutions [4]. IoV facilitates Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication, encompassing interactions between Vehicles-to-Vehicles (V2V), Vehicles-to-Infrastructure (V2I),

Vehicles-to-Pedestrians (V2P), and Vehicles-to-Roadside Infrastructure (V2R) [15]. For instance, if a vehicle detects road congestion ahead, it can relay this information to nearby vehicles approaching the congested area. This information allows vehicles to adjust their routes, collectively improving traffic flow.

With this advancement comes an increased risk of security threats targeting the interconnected vehicles and infrastructure. For example, the Jeep Cherokee remote hijacking incident [6] and Toyota RAV4 CAN (Controller Area Network) injection attack [27, 39] are a few examples highlighting emerging security threats targeting connected vehicles. To tackle such security challenges and enhance the security of the IoV requires exploring diverse strategies, e.g., proactive security solutions. Proactive security solutions are adept at identifying, detecting, and alerting to potential attacks [29]. One effective proactive security solution is using a deception system such as honeypots, honeynets, or decoys [7, 25]. These deception solutions intentionally lure attackers, enticing them into compromising scenarios and enabling the gathering of actionable intelligence on attackers' Techniques, Tactics, and Procedures (TTPs), thereby facilitating effective countermeasures.

However, such deception solutions encounter various challenges in effectively addressing security threats to IoV infrastructure posed by sophisticated attackers. For instance, honeypot-based deception often has limited interaction capabilities, offering basic responses to attackers and lacking realism to closely mimic real systems, thus making it easier for attackers to identify and evade [7, 28]. Also, they are complex and lack scalability, especially in IoV-based large and complex networks with numerous potential attack surfaces [10]. These shortcomings often lead to challenges in maintaining control over sensitive data generated by the IoV environment, increasing the risk of unauthorized access and data breaches [24]. Honeypots are standalone systems that do not integrate well with operational systems and processes of IoV, and it is challenging to analyze large volumes of generated data effectively [2, 28]. Furthermore, the deception solutions encounter secure communication, data integrity, and traceability challenges [17, 36]. This is particularly evident in protecting important information (e.g., deception rules, attackers' TTPs) against unauthorized access and modifications.

To address the aforementioned challenges of traditional deception solutions, we propose a proactive security approach for IoV by leveraging **DECEPT**-based **digital** **TW**ins and **blockchaIN** (DECEPTWIN). The contribution of this work is twofold: (i) We use Digital Twin (DT) technology to develop a deception solution specifically tailored for IoV, aiming to establish a realistic, dynamic, and interactive deception environment. (ii) We integrate blockchain within the proposed approach to overcome secure communication, data integrity, and traceability challenges.

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The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses deception, DT, blockchain, and related work. Section 3 presents the proposed deception solution and Section 4 is the realization of it during the attack. Section 5 is the discussion. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 PRELIMINARIES

This section overviews the deception (Section 2.1), DT (Section 2.2), and blockchain (Section 2.3). Also, it examines the related work (Section 2.4) to highlight the novelty of this work.

2.1 Deception

Deception is a proactive security strategy that employs tactics such as introducing misleading information, deploying decoy assets, or creating deceptive elements to induce uncertainty and confusion to divert, delay, or misguide attackers [11, 21]. Honeypots are deception-based solutions that serve as early warning systems by identifying and alerting organizations to the presence of attackers within their networks [21]. This technique diverts the attention of attackers away from the real system's assets and processes. It can also help to disrupt attacker workflows, forcing them to expend valuable time and effort on non-existent targets while minimizing the risk of real-world impact [35]. The deception environments are a rich source of TI, providing insights into attacker TTPs [11]. For instance, the deception solutions can provide forensic data and contextual information to support investigations and facilitate rapid incident triage and response, enabling security teams to contain and remediate threats effectively [30]. Additionally, the presence of deception raises the cost and complexity of conducting successful attacks, dissuading opportunistic attackers, and discouraging further infiltration and exploitation attempts [35].

2.2 Digital twin

DTs are virtual (digital) representations of physical objects, systems, or processes [3]. These virtual representations support continuous and accurate reflection of the physical entity for real-time monitoring, analysis, and simulation [3, 37]. DTs are not limited to a singular static representation but encompass the entire lifecycle of the physical object [26, 34]. For instance, they consist of components including physical and virtual models, connectivity for data exchange, data integration from various sources, interface for user interaction, lifecycle management, and security measures to ensure data confidentiality and integrity [34].

Numerous studies have delved into integrating DT technology as a security-enhancing enabler. These studies span across diverse domains, including industrial settings, Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), and smart infrastructure. For example, Xu et al. [37] employ DT technology as an anomaly detection platform within CPS, which relies on historical data to establish baseline behavior patterns and real-time data for continuous monitoring and detection of deviations from normal operations. Similarly, Eckhart et al. [9] utilize DT technology to enhance the security of smart factories by integrating security testing and intrusion detection capabilities of DT. Their approach utilizes the dynamic and interactive nature of DTs to simulate various security scenarios and test the resilience of systems against potential security threats.

In the context of deception, DTs create highly realistic deception environments by simulating the appearance, behavior, and functionality of real assets [33, 37]. DTs support the dynamic adaptation and evolution of deception environments, allowing security teams to adjust and refine deceptive tactics in response to evolving threats and attack scenarios. Through real-time monitoring and analysis capabilities, DTs empower security teams to discern patterns, trends, and anomalies in attacker interactions within the deception environment, thereby enabling proactive threat detection and response measures. Additionally, DTs contribute significantly to generating Threat Intelligence (TI) by capturing intricate details regarding attacker TTPs and objectives within the deceptive setting. This data enables security teams to extract actionable insights into emerging threats, attack vectors, and attacker profiles, maintaining situational awareness and guiding proactive security strategies. Furthermore, by maintaining detailed logs and metadata, DTs empower security teams to reconstruct attack scenarios, pinpoint the origins of security breaches, and conduct forensic analysis to identify root causes and devise effective countermeasures.

2.3 Blockchain

Blockchain has gained prominence due to the advent of Bitcoin [14, 23]. However, its applications have since expanded far beyond cryptocurrencies, offering a decentralized and secure solution for various industries that introduces a paradigm shift in how data is stored, verified, and shared across networks [13]. Blockchain is a decentralized, distributed, and immutable ledger technology that enables the secure and transparent recording of transactions across a network of computers [23]. Blockchain operates on a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) network, where each participant (node) maintains an identical copy of the ledger [14]. Transactions are grouped into blocks, and each block is linked to the previous one using unique cryptographic hashes, forming a chain of blocks. Blockchain uses consensus mechanisms to ensure that all nodes in a decentralized network maintain a consistent and immutable record of transactions without relying on the trusted authority [1, 14]. Various consensus mechanisms, such as Proof of Work (PoW), Proof of Stake (PoS), and Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT), are employed to achieve consensus [36]. Blockchain also introduces the concept of smart contracts, which are self-executing contracts with the terms of the agreement directly written into code [5]. Smart contracts automate and enforce the execution of contractual obligations, reducing the need for intermediaries and streamlining processes.

2.4 Related work

While there is limited exploration of blockchain and DT-based deception solutions for the IoV in existing literature, several studies have investigated related concepts within the IoV context.

2.4.1 Deception solutions for IoV. Existing studies have examined the honeypots-based deceptions in enhancing the security of IoV infrastructure. For example, honeypots within IoV are designed to lure and deceive potential attackers, providing valuable insights into their TTPs [2, 25]. Additionally, honeypots are used to detect and mitigate unauthorized remote access attempts, intra-vehicle network attacks, malware propagation, and Denial-of-Service (DoS)

attacks [7, 28, 29]. Despite highlighting honeypots-based deceptions as a proactive security measure for IoV, these studies also underscore their associated challenges. For example, configuring honeypots incurs additional overhead and costs associated with monitoring these deceptive systems [7, 25, 29]. Composing convincing honeypots that effectively deceive and engage attackers with the deception environment for a longer period presents a significant challenge. To overcome these challenges, the authors [7, 28] advocating for high-level interaction propose deploying a honeypot in a real car where the data from the host car is used to produce reasonable traffic within the deception network. Likewise, another study [2] developed a CAN honeypot for exchanging CAN traffic with the vehicle’s central server for a real-time simulation. However, such approaches pose elevated risks of security breaches, potentially resulting in data and privacy violations or even adverse physical consequences. Moreover, the implementation of these approaches is limited within a small number of vehicles due to the intricate integration required with the operational systems and processes of the IoV, as discussed in [2, 7, 28].

2.4.2 Blockchain as a security enabler for IoV and deception solutions. Various research works have utilized blockchain as a security enabler within the IoV infrastructure for secure V2V communication, decentralized authentication, and tamper-resistant data storage. For example, the authors [17, 36] ensure data integrity in the IoV system by decentralized consensus and tamper-proof characteristics of blockchain. Another work uses blockchain to establish trust and accountability in the IoV ecosystem by providing transparent and auditable records of interactions [8]. Furthermore, smart contracts enable the automated execution of predefined agreements, streamlining processes e.g., V2V communication, toll collection, and insurance claims within the IoV network [16].

Several research studies have also delved into the exploration of blockchain for deception solutions. For example, Abdulqadder et al. [1] present blockchain in edge-assisted honeypots, particularly focusing on user authentication and the preservation of authenticated users’ tokens to maintain their integrity. Another work [24] built a honeypot and blockchain-based intrusion detection and prevention model in edge computing. Shi et al. propose a dynamic distributed honeypot based on the Ethereum blockchain for strong and authenticating port access requests to mitigate eavesdropping, scanning, and DoS attacks [31]. While the aforementioned studies provide valuable insights into security mechanisms within the deception solutions using blockchain, there remains a gap in the literature regarding the integration of blockchain within DT-based deception solutions specifically tailored for IoV infrastructure.

2.4.3 Novelty of our work. In contrast to related works, our work utilizes DT-based deception techniques, which offer a high-level interaction through a realistic yet deceptive representation of physical systems and dynamic settings (Section 3.2.2). Furthermore, we integrate blockchain within the IoV-based deception to secure critical information, such as attackers’ TTPs executed in the deception environment, deception rules, deception data, attacker profiles, and LDT models (Section 3.2.3). Additionally, our approach is tailored to the IoV context, addressing the pressing security requirements within the ITS domain (Section 4). Thus, by aligning our approach with the specific needs of IoV security, we provide a proactive

security approach DECEPTWIN that contributes to the security resilience of the IoV infrastructure.

3 DECEPTWIN: THE PROPOSED APPROACH

The DECEPTWIN architecture (Fig. 1) illustrates a virtualized representation of the DT and blockchain-based deception solution for the IoV. The architecture consists of (i) internet and networking, (ii) physical system, (iii) deception environment, and (iv) blockchain segments. The Internet and networking encompass the configuration of decoy and baiting systems to lure and mislead potential attackers, directing them toward a deceptive environment. The physical system presents a complex and dynamic setting with interconnected vehicles, infrastructure, and communication systems. A Low-fidelity DT (LDT) based deception environment deploys deceptive elements to detect and deter malicious activities. For instance, the deception environment emulates key attributes and behaviors to create a convincing illusion for attackers. The integration of blockchain helps to secure and manage critical data.

In this work, our primary emphasis lies on the integration of the deception environment and blockchain. Consequently, we delve into the details of the specific components within these two segments, as outlined in Section 3.1. Additionally, we discuss the working of the DECEPTWIN, delineated in Section 3.2.

Figure 1: Schematic overview of DT and Blockchain-based deception solution, DECEPTWIN, in the IoV context.

3.1 DECEPTWIN components

The components constituting DECEPTWIN and their integration settings are structured across six stages, as depicted in Fig. 2 to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the proposed approach and the interconnections between its constituent elements.

3.1.1 Physical system settings. This phase (Stage 1 of Fig. 2) is responsible for creating High-fidelity DT (HDT) models derived from a reference DT, which serves as a blueprint of the physical system and encapsulates the essential characteristics, structure, and behavior of the physical system. The modeling of the reference DT is supported by process knowledge (as discussed in Algo. 2-Phase-I). The reference DT serves as the foundation for the deceptive DT instantiation process, enabling the creation of deceptive LDT

Figure 2: DECEPTWIN: Proactive security approach for IoV by leveraging deception-based DTs and blockchain.

models as elaborated in Section 3.1.3. To ensure the current state of the physical assets, the reference DT periodically performs the digital-physical mapping between the Physical Environment (PE) and its digital replica. Following the LDT model strategy, we ensure a demarcation between the deception environment and the physical system. This deliberate separation safeguards the attacker from gaining access to a physical system.

3.1.2 Crafting the trap. Crafting the trap (Stage 2 of Fig. 2) falls under the internet and networking segment of the DECEPTWIN. Traps divert attackers away from real systems and assets (discussed in Algo. 1). These traps include decoys, baiting, and breadcrumbs, which are crafted to entice and confound potential attackers. Decoys include fake credentials and data, dummy files, or simulated network services that appear real to attackers but are carefully monitored and controlled by security teams [38]. Baiting dangle enticing offers or opportunities to lure attackers into taking action, revealing their intentions or vulnerabilities [18, 38]. Breadcrumbs strategically scatter false clues or indicators across the network, leading attackers on a misleading path and away from valuable targets [18]. Each trap is strategically tailored to exploit attacker behavior and psychology to prolong their engagement with the

deception environment. In conjunction with crafting traps, implementing a firewall adds an extra layer of defense by distinguishing and routing trusted and untrusted network traffic [22]. Firewalls act as gatekeepers for network communication to analyze incoming and outgoing data packets based on predefined rules, allowing only authorized traffic to a physical system while diverting unauthorized traffic to a deceived environment.

3.1.3 Deception environment settings. The deception environment comprises three key steps: (i) deception modeling, (ii) deception execution, and (iii) deception revision (Stage 3 of Fig. 2).

Deception modeling (Stage 3.1 of Fig. 2) generates deceptive LDT models based on inputs including deception elements, scope, and deception settings (Algo. 2-Phase-II). The process of deception modeling initiates with the instantiation of a DT instance derived from the HDT model (Algo. 2-Step-2). The instantiated DT instance is then transmitted to the deception adapter for orchestrating the deception strategy (Algo. 2-Step-10 and 11). Within the deception adapter, detection settings retrieved from the blockchain are employed to define the parameters of the deception scope, encompassing various levels such as data, system, network, or application-level deception. Deception elements create a convincing illusion of the

real system, including fabricated data streams, documents, and credentials strategically positioned to lure attackers. Attack surfaces, representing vulnerable points within the system, are identified and simulated, spanning network segments, applications, and network devices. Furthermore, components such as APIs (Application Programming Interfaces), web services, and third-party services are introduced, closely mirroring the architecture and functionality of the real system. Through this comprehensive approach, the deception modeling process aims to create a highly realistic and dynamic deceptive environment.

Deception execution (Stage 3.2 of Fig. 2) involves the operational deployment of a deceptive LDT instance constructed from LDT models within a simulated environment (Algo. 2-Phase-III). It is characterized by active engagement mechanisms, including controls, operations, inputs, and interfaces, designed to make the deception as realistic as possible for the attacker.

Deception revision (Stage 3.3 of Fig. 2) is dedicated to refining and planning subsequent deception strategies based on the analysis of attacker actions and other relevant data and logs collected during the monitoring and tracking stage (refer to Section 3.1.4). It utilizes insights from the gathered TI (as outlined in Algo. 2-Phase-IV) to enhance the adaptiveness of the deception measures.

3.1.4 Monitoring and tracking. The monitoring and tracking (Stage 4 of Fig. 2) techniques within deception gather data based on the attacker’s movement and TTPs in the deception environment (Algo. 3-Phase-I). For example, these techniques encompass network traffic monitoring, which involves continuously analyzing data packets to detect anomalous patterns. Attacker footprints refer to the digital traces left behind by attackers as they navigate through the deception environment. Metadata collection gathers contextual information about network traffic, attacker interactions, and system events. Compliance checks are conducted to ensure adherence to security policies, regulatory requirements, and best practices. In parallel with monitoring, the tracking phase focuses on logging events, activities, and TTPs exhibited by the attacker. Every interaction and action performed within the deception environment is recorded on the blockchain (Algo. 3-Step 11), providing a comprehensive and immutable trail of the attacker’s activities. Through monitoring and tracking, practical insights are gleaned into attackers’ methods, objectives, and potential vulnerabilities exploited that can enable security teams to understand the evolving threat landscape. Furthermore, the accumulated data and logs serve as a valuable resource for post-incident analysis, facilitating forensic investigations, attribution efforts, and the refinement of deception strategy (refer to deception revision, Stage 3.3 of Fig. 2).

3.1.5 Analysis and reporting. This phase (Stage 5 of Fig. 2) of the DECEPTWIN conducts TI to generate an attacker profile by utilizing the insights based on the attacker’s behavior and TTPs (Algo. 3-Phase-II). The TI process involves aggregating and analyzing data collected during the monitoring and tracking phase to identify patterns, trends, and Indicators of Compromise (IoCs) associated with the attacker’s activities (Algo. 3-Step 7). By correlating disparate pieces of information, such as network traffic patterns, system events, and attacker behavior, a comprehensive profile of the attacker is constructed (Algo. 3-Step 8). This profile encapsulates key attributes of the attacker, including their tactics, preferred attack

vectors, and objectives, providing valuable intelligence for defensive strategies and IR. The collected deception data, including TI and attacker profiles, can be presented through reports or visualizations, facilitating the interpretation and dissemination of actionable intelligence to relevant stakeholders. For example, this can enable security teams to gain deeper insights into emerging threats, prioritize response efforts, and enhance situational awareness within the IoV environment (Algo. 3-Step 9). Moreover, to ensure the integrity and accessibility of the attacker profile, it is stored on the blockchain to establish a tamper-resistant and auditable record of the attacker’s characteristics (Algo. 3-Step 11).

3.1.6 Storage (Off-chain and On-chain). The storage layer (Stage 6 of Fig. 2) leverages blockchain to ensure the integrity and security of the deception environment’s data (Algo. 3-Phase-III). To address the scalability challenges related to storage and performance inherent in blockchain technology [12], we adopt a dual approach confining off-chain and on-chain techniques. Off-chain maintains deception data and rules, logs, metadata, LDT models, and attacker profiles to support comprehensive record-keeping and analysis (Algo. 3-Step 10). On-chain maintains the hashes of these elements to leverage the blockchain’s inherent security features for data integrity and verification purposes (Algo. 3-Step 11). Blockchain networks are detached from external data sources, however, blockchain oracles can facilitate the transfer of off-chain data onto the blockchain, enabling interaction between decentralized systems and real-world events [19]. Additionally, smart contracts are employed to build decentralized and distributed access controls to ensure that no unauthorized user (insider or outsider) can access or manipulate deception environment configurations (Algo. 3-Step 12).

3.2 How does the DECEPTWIN operate?

This section elucidates the operational functionality of DECEPTWIN through algorithmic representations. The algorithms outlined herein delineate how DECEPTWIN crafts traps (Algo. 1), employs DT-based deception to fortify network defenses (Algo. 2), as well as monitoring, analysis, and data storage management (Algo. 3).

3.2.1 Algorithm 1. Algo. 1 outlines a process for crafting traps in a $D_{environment}$. Initially, the algorithm takes as input network traffic data and configurations for decoy systems. It then iterates through each N_{pkt} , checking for matches with predefined suspicious activity rules ($Sup_{rules}^{activity}$). Upon detecting suspicious activity, the algorithm identifies the IP_{target} from the N_{pkt} and selects an appropriate $D_{environment}$ based on predefined $D_{strategy}^i$. Subsequently, it forwards the attacker to the selected $D_{environment}$.

3.2.2 Algorithm 2. Algo. 2 discusses the modeling, deployment, and revision of deceptive DTs. Phase I creates a reference DT (DT_{ref}) digital representation of the Physical Environment (PE). From DT_{ref} , HDT models (HDT_{models}^i) are derived that showcase various assets, processes, or services depending on the underlying use case. Note that HDT_{models}^i must exhibit sufficient fidelity as discussed in [32]. To generate HDT_{models}^i , process knowledge (P_k) provides necessary input data sources and other supporting services such as Knowledge Base (KB), machine learning models (ML_{models}), and Infrastructure as Code (IaC). KB contains historical data and

Table 1: Summary of notations.

Notation	Explanation	Notation	Explanation
D_{scope}	Deception scope	$D_{element}^i$	i^{th} Deception element
D_{data}	Deception data	$D_{adapter}$	Deception adapter
$D_{environment}$	Deception environment	$Decoy_{configs}$	Decoy configurations
DD_{layer}	Deception deployment layer	$D_{strategy}^i$	i^{th} Deception strategy
$N_{traffic}$	Network traffic data	$Sup_{rules}^{activity}$	Suspicious activity rules
N_{pkt}	Network traffic packet	IP_{target}	Target IP address
LDT_{models}^i	i^{th} Low-fidelity DT models	HDT_{models}^i	i^{th} High-fidelity DT models
Sim_{env}	Simulation environment	PE	Physical Environment
$A_{control}$	Access control	P_k	Process knowledge
$S_{contract}$	Smart contract	ML_{models}	Machine Learning models

Algorithm 1 Crafting the trap based on decoys.

```

1: Input:  $N_{traffic}, Decoy_{configs}$ 
2: Output: Deception system with crafted traps
3:  $N_{pkt} \leftarrow N_{traffic}$  ▷ Monitoring  $N_{pkt}$  through firewall.
4: for each  $N_{pkt}$  do
5:   if  $N_{pkt}$  matches with defined  $Sup_{rules}^{activity}$  then
6:     Identify  $IP_{target}$  from  $N_{pkt}$ 
7:     Select  $D_{element}^i$  based on  $D_{strategy}^i$  (Call Algo. 2-Phase-I and II)
8:     Forward attacker to  $D_{environment}$ 
9:   end if
10: end for

```

system specifications whereas real-time sensor ($sensor_{data}^i$) and asset data ($assets_{data}^i$) can be obtained from PE . ML_{models} support analyzing the vast amounts of data generated by DTs. IaC can be defined to host DT models efficiently. Tools such as Azure Resource Manager (ARM) exemplify IaC by providing the necessary hosting infrastructure such as virtual machines, containers, network settings, etc., essential for operational deployment of DTs [20]. The defined configurations can be version-controlled and reused, thereby making it easier to deploy and scale DT environments.

Phase II involves modeling LDT models (LDT_{models}^i). The prerequisites for this phase include fetching predefined deception rules (D_{rules}) and attacker KB ($Attacker_{KB}$) from storage (Algo. 3-Phase-III). D_{rules} define factors necessary for enhancing the efficacy and resilience of the deception strategies. It includes the strategic placement of deception elements ($D_{element}^i$) such as synthetic data generation, simulated attack surfaces, decoy services, or utilities in connection with the defined deception scope (D_{scope}). Depending on the objective and available resources, a deception can accommodate single or multiple levels D_{scope} at the data, system, software, or application level. D_{rules} specify temporal-based configurations, i.e., the duration for which the deceptive twin will remain active and interactive within the simulated deception environment (Sim_{env}).

D_{rules} incorporate compliance-related directives, outlining the specific logs and deception data (D_{data}) that must be captured during the deception execution phase for post-operation analysis. Furthermore, D_{rules} include provisions for alerting mechanisms, specifying which stakeholders should be notified in the event of interactions or breaches. $Attacker_{KB}$ such as MITRE ATT&CK is utilized to integrate known attacker TTPs and IoCs to respective $D_{element}^i$. This step aims to make the $D_{element}^i$ realistic and engaging by mimicking the artifacts that attackers expect to find after they have compromised a system or network. The next step is to load the deception adapter ($D_{adapter}$) with crafted and acquired deception settings such as D_{rules} , D_{scope} along with its $D_{element}^i$, and $Attacker_{KB}$. $D_{adapter}$ can be loaded to LDT_{models}^i where LDT_{models}^i can be instantiated from $HDT_{models}^i \subset DT_{ref}$. To ensure the integrity of LDT_{models}^i , generated models are also archived (Algo. 3-Phase-III).

Phase III involves the execution of $LDT_{instance}^i$ (instantiated from LDT_{models}^i) in a controlled simulated environment (Sim_{env}). The main step is the development of $Interface$ with proper $Controls$, $Operations$, $Inputs$, and $Communications$ that makes the Sim_{env} highly interactive and realistically challenging for attackers. $Controls$ constrained attacker's behavior by providing them with available options for interaction, which could include simulated network configurations, decoy systems, or interactive prompts. $Inputs$ refers to data or commands such as command-line instructions, network packets, or any form of data entry by the attacker during their interaction with Sim_{env} . $Inputs$ are critical for making Sim_{env} responsive and for capturing the attacker's TTPs. $Operations$ refers to the simulated functions and actions that the environment supports or mimics in response to the attacker's $Inputs$. $Operations$ could simulate responses of systems, networks, or applications to the attacker's actions, creating an illusion of real interactions and consequences. $Communications$ refers to the exchange of information between Sim_{env} and the attacker. It consists of feedback given to the attacker as a result of their actions through $Operations$ or

Algorithm 2 Modeling, deployment, and revision of deceptive DTs.**Input:** $sensor_{data}^i$, $asset_{data}^i$, P_k (KB , ML_{models} , IaC), $Attacker_{KB}$ (IoCs, TTPs), D_{rules} , D_{data} , $D_{element}^i$, $A_{control}$ **Output:** DT_{ref} , LDT_{models}^i **Phase I: Generate HDT_{models}^i as a DT_{ref}**

- 1: To model and develop HDT_{models}^i as a DT_{ref} :
 - a: Obtain real-time data $sensor_{data}^i$ and $asset_{data}^i$ from PE
 - b: Obtain trained ML_{models} from P_k
 - c: Define IaC from P_k for hosting HDT_{models}^i ▷ IaC : virtual machines, containers, network settings, storage, etc.

Phase II: Model LDT_{models}^i

- 2: Instantiate LDT_{models}^i from $HDT_{models}^i \subset DT_{ref}$
- 3: **for** each LDT_{models}^i **do**
- 4: Fetch D_{rules} from $Offchain$ (Call Algo. 3)
- 5: Check conformance of D_{rules} with $A_{control}$ ▷ $A_{control}$: Policies and Mechanisms
- 6: Fetch $Attacker_{KB}$ from $Offchain$ (Call Algo. 3)
- 7: Determine D_{scope} (single or multiple) ▷ D_{scope} : Data, System, Network, Application.
- 8: Develop $D_{element}^i$ within the determined D_{scope} ▷ $D_{element}^i$: synthetic data generation, simulated attack surfaces, and decoys
- 9: Integrate IoCs/TTPs from $Attacker_{KB}$ to respective $D_{element}^i$
- 10: $D_{adapter} \leftarrow D_{rules}, Attacker_{KB}, D_{scope}, D_{element}^i$
- 11: Load $D_{adapter}$ to LDT_{models}^i
- 12: **end for**
- 13: Store LDT_{models}^i (Call Algo. 3)

Phase III: Execute $LDT_{instance}^i$

- 14: To set up Sim_{env} for $LDT_{instance}^i \subset LDT_{models}^i$:
 - a: Define $Controls$, $Operations$, and $Inputs$ ▷ Simulation parameters essential to make Sim_{env} interactive.
 - b: $Interface \leftarrow \{Controls, Operations, Inputs, Communications\}$
 - c: $Sim_{env} \leftarrow Interface$
 - d: Load Sim_{env} to $LDT_{instance}^i$

Phase IV: Revise deception artifacts of LDT_{models}^i

- 15: **for** each LDT_{models}^i **do**
- 16: Revise $D_{strategy}^i$ based on:
 - a: DD_{layer} ▷ DD_{layer} based on D_{scope}
 - b: $Attacker_{state}^{current}$ from $Attacker_{profile}$ (Call Algo. 3)
 - c: D_{data} from previously executed DT-based Deception(s) (Call Algo. 3)
- 17: **end for**

Inputs. Finally, Sim_{env} is loaded to $LDT_{instance}^i$, which acts as a decoy system for potential attackers.

Phase IV involves the revision of deception artifacts for the next LDT_{models}^i . This step is crucial because deception strategies ($D_{strategy}^i$) must evolve to remain effective. Static or unchanging $D_{element}^i$ risk becoming predictable, allowing attackers to recognize and bypass them in future encounters. To effectively revise LDT_{models}^i , $D_{strategy}^i$ must rely on deceptive deployment layer (DD_{layer}) in connection with defined D_{scope} , $Attacker_{state}^{current}$ obtained from $Attacker_{profile}$ (as discussed in Algo. 3), and D_{data} .

3.2.3 Algorithm 3. Algo. 3 discusses data monitoring, analysis and storage. Phase I involves monitoring and tracking of $LDT_{instance}^i$ in the form of deception data (D_{data}), logging events, activities, and TTPs ($logs$), and metadata ($meta$). D_{data} holds critical information on traffic monitoring and the traces left by attackers, which are instrumental in deciphering the routes and methods employed by

attackers to probe and interact with the deceptive environment. $meta$, on the other hand, enriches D_{data} by providing additional context and insights on attacker interactions within the deceptive setup. At this stage, data is also archived for further analysis.

Phase II involves the analysis and reporting of gathered data during the monitoring and tracking phase. To analyze data, TI is performed as follows. First, threat data ($Threat_{data}$) is aggregated from various sources, including D_{data} , $logs$, and $Attacker_{KB}$ reflecting the current threat landscape and attacker behaviors. Second, ML_{models} are leveraged to obtain $Processed_{Threat}^{data}$. This processing step is essential for filtering, correlating, and enriching threat data to extract meaningful insights. Third, $Processed_{Threat}^{data}$ is analyzed to uncover critical insights, such as emerging threat patterns, attacker tactics, and potential vulnerabilities. This analysis helps in identifying imminent threats and triggering alerts for timely intervention. By understanding the nuances of $Processed_{Threat}^{data}$, security teams can make informed decisions to preemptively counteract or mitigate

Algorithm 3 Monitoring, analysis, and data storage management.**Input:** $LDT_{instance}^i$ **Output:** $Offchain, Onchain, Attacker_{profile}$ **Phase I: Monitoring and Tracking**

- 1: **do**
- 2: Capture and archive D_{data}
- 3: Capture and archive $logs$
- 4: Archive $meta$
- 5: Conduct compliance verification against $A_{control}$
- 6: **while** ($LDT_{instance}^i == \text{active}$)

- ▷ D_{data} : traffic monitoring, attacker footprints
- ▷ $logs$: events, activities, TTPs/IoCs.
- ▷ $meta$ related to D_{data} and $logs$.

Phase II: Analysis and Reporting

- 7: To conduct TI :
 - a: Obtain $Threat_{data}$ from $D_{data}, logs, Attacker_{KB}(IoCs, TTPs)$
 - b: $Processed_{Threat}^{data} = Threat_{data} \leftarrow ML_{models}$
 - c: Analyze insights and trigger alerts
 - d: Disseminate actionable insights with communities
- 8: To build $Attacker_{profile}$:
 - a: Analyze attack patterns from $Processed_{Threat}^{data}$ and $Attacker_{KB}$
 - b: Classify attackers based on motivation, skill set, preferred attack methods, targets, and behavioral characteristics
 - c: Refine $Attacker_{profile}$
- 9: Generate reports or visualize data

- ▷ Apply ML_{models} to processed $Threat_{data}$
- ▷ $Attacker_{KB}$
- ▷ Classification: nation-state, cybercriminals, hacktivist, etc.

Phase III: Storage ($Offchain$ and $Onchain$)

- 10: $Offchain \leftarrow D_{rules}, D_{data}, logs, meta, LDT_{models}^i, Attacker_{profile}$
- 11: $Onchain \leftarrow hash\{D_{rules}\}, hash\{D_{data}\}, hash\{logs\}, hash\{meta\}, hash\{LDT_{model}^i\}, hash\{Attacker_{profile}\}$
- 12: $\{S_{contract}\} \Rightarrow A_{control}$

security threats. Fourth, actionable insights are shared with relevant communities and stakeholders. The next key step is to construct an attacker profile ($Attacker_{profile}$) as follows. First, attack patterns are analyzed, utilizing processed threat data ($Processed_{Threat}^{data}$) and existing entries within the Attacker KB ($Attacker_{KB}$). This comprehensive analysis aims to identify, catalog, and understand the evolving TTPs employed by attackers. Second, attackers are classified based on their underlying motivations (e.g., financial gain, political agenda), skill sets (e.g., technical proficiency, social engineering capabilities), preferred methods of attack (e.g., malware deployment, phishing campaigns), specific targets (e.g., financial institutions, government entities), and observable behavioral characteristics. Such classification includes but is not limited to, nation-states, cybercriminals, and hacktivists, allowing for a nuanced understanding of the threat landscape. Third, refinement of $Attacker_{profile}$ based on the insights gained from attack pattern analysis and attacker classification. These profiles are updated to reflect the most current understanding of an attacker’s capabilities, intentions, and operational patterns. Additionally, this phase facilitates the creation of detailed reports and the visualization of deception insights, enabling security teams to examine the TTPs utilized by attackers, alongside their interactions within the deceptive environment.

Phase III involves data storage management ($Offchain$ and $Onchain$), ensuring the integrity and immutability of the operational data critical to the deceptive twin infrastructure. The data including $D_{rules}, D_{data}, logs, meta, LDT_{models}^i$, and $Attacker_{profile}$ are stored $Offchain$ to address storage and performance issues of blockchain platforms whereas the hash of data is stored $Onchain$ (Stage 6 of Fig. 2). Smart

contracts ($S_{contract}$) are employed to implement decentralized and distributed access controls ($A_{control}$). For instance, $A_{control}$ governs which stakeholders can access or alter D_{rules} . Such controls are essential in safeguarding against unauthorized interventions or alterations, particularly from insiders who might otherwise undermine the efficacy and integrity of the deceptive environment.

4 ATTACK SCENARIO AND ROLE OF DECEPTWIN

This section discusses the IoV remote access attack scenario and details the various stages of the attack (Section 4.1). Also, it delves into the role of DECEPTWIN during this attack (Section 4.2).

4.1 IoV remote access

We devise a remote access attack scenario targeting the vehicles within IoV to infiltrate the onboard systems of vehicles or their connected infrastructure from a remote location. The attacker capitalizes on vulnerabilities such as weak authentication mechanisms, injecting malicious code via over-the-air (OTA) updates, or intercepting and tampering with wireless communications. Through these means, the attacker can remotely manipulate vehicle functionalities, compromise user data, or disrupt the normal operations of vehicles within the IoV network. During this attack, we simulate a situation that convinces the attacker they have successfully infiltrated the actual system. Subsequently, the attacker engages in a series of activities mirroring those typically performed within a real system. These activities include different stages of the cyber attack

Figure 3: Realization of DECEPTWIN during the remote access attack on a vehicle within IoV environment.

lifecycle, such as reconnaissance, weaponization, exploitation, command and control, exfiltration, and covering his tracks. In reconnaissance, the attacker gathers information about potential targets and vulnerabilities within the IoV network. Subsequently, the attacker proceeds to weaponize their findings, developing or acquiring tools and techniques to exploit identified vulnerabilities. The exploitation phase leverages these tools to gain unauthorized access to IoV systems, followed by establishing command and control channels to maintain persistence and issue malicious commands. Furthermore, the attacker executes exfiltration maneuvers to retrieve valuable data from compromised IoV assets, such as sensitive user information or telemetry data. Finally, to evade detection and cover his tracks, the attacker engages in activities aimed at concealing their presence and obscuring forensic evidence of the attack.

4.2 Role of DECEPTWIN

Throughout the cyber attack lifecycle, the DECEPTWIN closely mimics the behavior and responses of a real IoV system, providing a realistic backdrop for the attacker’s actions. For example, during the reconnaissance, DECEPTWIN generates LDT, incorporating authentic yet misleading details such as remote access functionalities and CAN bus communication protocols. By accurately simulating the behavior and attributes of IoV systems, DECEPTWIN embeds deceptive elements to trick attackers into believing they have successfully weaponized their tools and payloads. These high-interaction deception elements simulate vulnerable entry points, enticing the attacker to reveal their TTPs. Upon successful weaponization, DECEPTWIN emulates the behavior of a compromised IoV network to lure attackers into exploiting simulated vulnerabilities. Subsequently, DECEPTWIN implements simulated command and control channels to emulate how attackers establish covert communication with compromised vehicles, leading the attacker to believe they have established control over compromised assets. Next, DECEPTWIN creates simulated data exfiltrations to replicate how attackers steal and transmit data from compromised vehicles. Lastly,

DECEPTWIN generates deceptive logs and traces to mislead attackers during the covering tracks phase to replicate how attackers attempt to evade detection and hide their activities.

Moreover, DECEPTWIN integrates monitoring and tracking to capture and retain attacker activities, TTPs, and objectives. These capabilities enable the DECEPTWIN to gather intelligence on reconnaissance and weaponization strategies, monitor exploitation attempts, command and control operations, attacker exfiltration methods, and covering-the-tracks techniques. To ensure the integrity and security of this captured data, blockchain technology is employed, facilitating the recording and verification of actions and interactions within the deception environment. Additionally, blockchain stores deception data, settings, and rules, as well as maintains attacker profiles and access control mechanisms.

5 DISCUSSION

The practical significance of deception solutions lies in their ability to enhance security across various domains by simulating realistic but deceptive scenarios to mislead and thwart attackers. In accordance with this, DECEPTWIN offers several key practical implications. For example, (i) proactive threat detection to proactively detect and thwart security threats by creating dynamic and realistic deception. By mimicking the behavior and characteristics of real assets, DT can lure attackers into revealing their presence and intentions, allowing security teams to identify and respond to threats. (ii) Intelligence gathering on evolving security threats and attackers’ behavior. (iii) Better understanding of the attack surfaces, identifying vulnerabilities, and testing the defenses in a safe and controlled environment. (iv) Cost-effective security testing simulating realistic attack scenarios within DT, organizations can evaluate the effectiveness of their security controls and refine their strategies without risking real-world assets or operations.

Limitations: One limitation of this work is the absence of practical implementation, which hinders the ability to demonstrate the

real-world effectiveness and applicability of DECEPTWIN. Moreover, DECEPTWIN applicability may vary depending on the specific context, industry, and threat landscape. Therefore, applicability validation is utmost for addressing the organization's unique security requirements. To do so, this may involve conducting pilot deployments and conducting risk assessments to evaluate the relevance of DECEPTWIN as a security strategy.

Future Work: One future work is conducting real-world pilot deployments and case studies to demonstrate the DECEPTWIN's effectiveness and applicability in diverse security contexts. Additionally, exploring innovative techniques for enhancing the practicality of DECEPTWIN, such as leveraging artificial intelligence, machine learning, and automation (e.g., IaC) to streamline deployment, configuration, and management processes.

6 CONCLUSION

This research has explored the DT and blockchain-based deception solution DECEPTWIN to enhance the security of the IoV infrastructure. DECEPTWIN offers promising avenues for addressing the multifaceted challenges encountered by traditional deception solutions, such as honeypots, in securing IoV infrastructure. DT-based deception can provide high-fidelity representations of IoV systems, enhancing realism and effectiveness in deceiving attackers while facilitating comprehensive monitoring and analysis of attacker behavior, activities, TTPs, and objectives employed during the attack. Through the realization of DECEPTWIN, we contend that this approach informs proactive security strategies, enabling security teams and organizations to better prepare for and mitigate potential security threats.

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